

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS OF THE FERGANA
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INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON LINGUISTICS & TRANSLATION
Scientific Open Access Conference**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 25th February 2026Accepted: 26th February 2026Online: 27th February 2026**KEYWORDS**

Fergana Jadidism, socio-philosophical views, enlightenment, national awakening, human dignity, civil society, spiritual heritage, development, free thinking, New Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the socio-philosophical views of representatives of the Fergana Jadid school and their role in the process of national consciousness and spiritual awakening. The Fergana Jadid movement, formed at the beginning of the 20th century, was based on the ideas of liberating the people from ignorance, bringing the nation to the path of development through science and enlightenment. The study analyzes the views of the Jadids on human dignity, enlightenment, free thinking, social justice, and national identity from a philosophical point of view. The author, on a scientific basis, highlights that the activities of the Fergana Jadids are inextricably linked with the policy of spiritual revival of modern Uzbekistan, in particular, the idea of "New Uzbekistan - a society where human dignity is glorified."

Entrance

In the history of Uzbekistan, the Jadid movement, as a unique spiritual, cultural, and philosophical phenomenon, marked the beginning of a period of national consciousness awakening. This movement, which emerged at the beginning of the 20th century, was essentially aimed at liberating the people from ignorance, backwardness, and the effects of colonialism, leading them towards enlightenment and progress.

During this period, the Fergana Valley became one of the most active centers of Jadidism. Through their activities, works, and ideas, the Fergana Jadids demonstrated dedication to awakening the nation, promoting human dignity, the right to free thought, and social justice.

Their socio-philosophical views are directly consonant with the ideas of today's New Uzbekistan - the concept of human dignity, free thought, tolerance, and the enhancement of civic consciousness. Therefore, the legacy of the Fergana Jadids is being studied as an important source in the development of modern socio-philosophical thought.

Fergana Jadidism, by its very nature, was an enlightenment-democratic movement, which called on the people to decide their own destiny, to realize national identity. The Jadids of Fergana considered man the highest value. In their opinion, for a person to realize their abilities, they need to be given the opportunity for knowledge, enlightenment, and free thinking. "The most essential things for a person are knowledge and morality. Because morality without knowledge, knowledge without morality cannot elevate society."

These ideas, along with calling a person to spiritual perfection, also form the basis of the philosophy of modern education.

At the center of the philosophical views of the Jadids are the issues of man, his intellect, free thinking, and spiritual maturity. For them, man is the main subject of social development, the center of changes in society. The Jadids of Fergana considered man the highest value. In their opinion, for a person to realize their abilities, they need to be given the opportunity for knowledge, enlightenment, and free thinking. These ideas, along with calling a person to spiritual perfection, also form the basis of the philosophy of modern education.

The main slogan of the Jadids was "Saving the Nation with Science." They saw science as the only way to national revival. The Fergana Jadids paid special attention to the issue of social justice. In their opinion, the development of society should be based on equality, respect, and harmony between people.

Furthermore, the Jadids promoted the idea of national awakening and sought to unite the people through knowledge of their history, language, and culture.

The Fergana Jadids are intellectuals who left a deep mark on the spiritual and philosophical thinking of their time. Their socio-philosophical views encouraged the people towards science, justice, free thought, national awakening, and civic responsibility.

Today's New Uzbekistan concept is based on the principles of human dignity, spirituality, freedom of thought, and justice. This is a continuation of the path to the society that the Jadids dreamed of - an enlightened, just, and humane civil society. Therefore, it would not be an exaggeration to say that the philosophy of the Fergana Jadids has become a spiritual compass not of the last century, but of today.

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